

Supporting Information

Large live biomass carbon losses from droughts in the northern temperate ecosystems during 2016-2022

Xiaojun Li^{1,2,*}, Philippe Ciais³, Rasmus Fensholt⁴, Jérôme Chave⁵, Stephen Sitch⁶, Josep G Canadell⁷, Martin Brandt⁴, Lei Fan⁸, Xiangming Xiao⁹, Shengli Tao¹⁰, Huan Wang¹⁰, Clément Albergel¹¹, Hui Yang¹⁰, Frédéric Frappart¹, Mengjia Wang¹², Ana Bastos¹³, Philippe Maisongrande¹⁴, Yuanwei Qin¹⁵, Zanpin Xing¹, Tianxiang Cui¹⁶, Ling Yu⁸, Lei He¹⁷, Yi Zheng^{1,18}, Xiangzhuo Liu¹, Yuqing Liu¹, Aurelien De Truchis¹⁹, Jean-Pierre Wigneron^{1,*}

¹ INRAE, Bordeaux Sciences Agro, UMR 1391 ISPA, Villenave-d'Ornon, France

² Faculty of Geosciences and Engineering, Southwest Jiaotong University, Chengdu 611756, China

³ Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, LSCE/IPSL, CEA-CNRS-UVSQ, Université Paris-Saclay, Gif-sur-Yvette, France

⁴ Department of Geoscience and Natural Resource Management, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

⁵ Centre de Recherche Biodiversité Environnement, CNRS, IRD, Université de Toulouse, INPT, Toulouse, France

⁶ Faculty of Environment, Science and Economy, University of Exeter, Exeter, UK

⁷ Global Carbon Project, CSIRO Environment, Canberra, ACT 2601, Australia

⁸ Chongqing Jinpo Mountain Karst Ecosystem National Observation and Research Station, School of Geographical Sciences, Southwest University, Chongqing, China

⁹ School of Biological Sciences, University of Oklahoma, Norman, OK 73019, USA

¹⁰ Institute of Ecology, College of Urban and Environmental Sciences, State Key Laboratory for Vegetation Structure, Function and Construction (VegLab), Peking University, Beijing 100871, China

¹¹ European Space Agency Climate Office, ECSAT, Didcot, UK

¹² School of Geoscience and Technology, Zhengzhou University, Zhengzhou 450001, China

¹³ Institute for Earth System Science and Remote Sensing, Leipzig University, Talstr. 35, 04103 Leipzig, Germany

¹⁴ Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales, Toulouse, France

¹⁵ Jiangsu Key Laboratory of Soil and Water Processes in Watershed, College of Geography and Remote Sensing, Hohai University, Nanjing 211000, China

¹⁶ Co-Innovation Center for Sustainable Forestry in Southern China, Nanjing Forestry University, Nanjing, Jiangsu 210042, China

¹⁷ State Key Laboratory of Efficient Utilization of Arable Land in China, Institute of Agricultural Resources and Regional Planning, Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Beijing 100081, China

¹⁸ School of Atmospheric Sciences, Southern Marine Science and Engineering Guangdong Laboratory (Zhuhai), Sun Yat-sen University, Zhuhai 519082, Guangdong, China

¹⁹ Kayrros SAS, Paris 75009, France

Corresponding authors: Xiaojun.li@inrae.fr; Jean-Pierre.Wigneron@inrae.fr

Supplementary Text

Text S1. New filtering method for SMOS-IC L-VOD data

Previous studies applied an efficient but simple method to filter L-VOD data using the root mean square of the measured and simulated brightness temperature (referred to as RMSE-TB). The good performance of this filtering method has been confirmed in the pan-tropical regions (Qin et al., 2021; Wigneron et al., 2020) and in Siberian regions (Fan et al., 2023). In this study, in addition to RMSE-TB, we used a novel and more rigorous method (Yang et al., 2023) recently developed by Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement (LSCE) and INRAE to triple-filter the daily SMOS-IC L-VOD data for both ascending (ASC) and descending (DESC) orbits (Fig. S23). The filtering method includes the following steps:

- (i) Remove the daily L-VOD data with $\text{RMSE-TB} > 8 \text{ K}$ and $\text{SF} > 1$, here SF is Scene Flag and $\text{SF} > 1$ corresponding to the pixels impacted by strong topography, pixel heterogeneity (e.g., water and urban fractions) and presence of frozen conditions (e.g., snow, ice); $\text{RMSE-TB} > 8 \text{ K}$ corresponding to the pixels affected by a large RFI event.
- (ii) Even though the L-VOD data with $\text{RMSE-TB} > 8 \text{ K}$ are excluded, the L-VOD data may still be affected by RFI. The large difference between the ASC and DESC data can be an indication of the potential pixels with bad quality of L-VOD data as demonstrated by (Al-Yaari et al., 2020). To better account for this, we divide the L-VOD sequence into multiple trimesters (three-month period). For each trimester, we calculate the average of the remaining L-VOD data within the trimester from ASC and DESC orbits, respectively. When their difference is larger than 0.05 K, we calculate the average of RMSE-TB with the trimester – if the average of RMSE-TB from ASC (or DESC) orbit is larger than 5k, we remove all the L-VOD data from ASC (or DESC) within this trimester.
- (iii) For each trimester, we calculate the mean and standard deviation (STD) of all the remaining L-VOD data and then exclude the outliers, i.e., data fall outside of $\text{mean} \pm 2\text{STD}$, which applies to both ASC and DESC data.

An assessment of the effectiveness of the new filtering method can be found in Yang et al. (2023). After these three filtering steps, only high-quality daily VOD observations were retained. On this basis, we finally used the median method to obtain robust annual estimates following (Brandt, et al., 2018; Fan et al., 2019; Wigneron et al., 2020).

Text S2. L-VOD correction for the effects of the vegetation moisture content (RWC)

2.1 Rationale for correcting the effects of RWC in L-VOD

L-VOD not only reflects the vegetation biomass, but also potentially the vegetation moisture content dynamics (Konings et al., 2019). Although the latter contribution to annual changes in L-VOD in tropical intact forests has been shown to be small (Yang et al., 2022), we consider this potential effect more thoroughly here to avoid the potential contribution of changes in vegetation moisture content on changes in L-VOD in the study area (i.e., the northern ecosystems). To achieve this, we used a simple multiplicative model, noting that vegetation water content (VWC) scales with both dry biomass (AGB) and the amount of water per unit biomass (relative water content, RWC) following previous studies (Yang et al., 2022; Momen et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2019). The rationale for this method is that L-VOD is linearly proportional to VWC as follows (Jackson & Schmugge, 1991):

$$\text{L-VOD} = b \times \text{VWC} = b \times \text{AGB} \times \text{RWC} \quad (1)$$

where b is a scaled slope that depends on the canopy structure and electromagnetic frequency. At L-band, the variation of b with time has been shown to be very small and is therefore often considered time invariant (Wigneron et al., 2004).

Previous studies suggest that leaf biomass can be estimated using vegetation indices such as normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) as a proxy (Fan et al., 2009; Potithepa et al., 2010), while RWC of different plant components can be linearly related to their leaf water potential (ψ_L) (Konings & Gentine, 2017). Thus, Eq. (1) can be written as:

$$\text{L-VOD} = b \times \text{AGB} \times \text{RWC} = b \times (p \cdot \text{NDVI} + s) \times (m \cdot \psi_L + n) \quad (2)$$

where p, s, m, n are empirical parameters that change in space but not over time. In this study, in order to reduce the potential contribution of changes in vegetation moisture content to changes in L-VOD, we built seven multiple regressions of L-VOD against NDVI and two vegetation moisture content proxies as follows:

$$\text{L-VOD} = \mu + \kappa \cdot \text{NDVI} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{L-VOD} = \nu + l \cdot \text{NDWI} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{L-VOD} = \mu + \kappa \cdot \text{SWC} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{L-VOD} = \alpha + \beta \cdot \text{NDWI} + \gamma \cdot \text{SWC} + \eta \cdot \text{NDWI} \times \text{SWC} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{L-VOD} = \alpha + \beta \cdot \text{NDVI} + \gamma \cdot \text{SWC} + \eta \cdot \text{NDVI} \times \text{SWC} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{L-VOD} = \alpha + \beta \cdot \text{NDVI} + \gamma \cdot \text{NDWI} + \eta \cdot \text{NDVI} \times \text{NDWI} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{L-VOD} = & \alpha + \beta \cdot \text{NDVI} + \gamma \cdot \text{NDWI} + \delta \cdot \text{SWC} + \eta_1 \cdot \text{NDVI} \times \text{NDWI} + \\ & \eta_2 \cdot \text{NDVI} \times \text{SWC} + \eta_3 \cdot \text{NDWI} \times \text{SWC} + \eta_4 \cdot \text{NDVI} \times \text{NDWI} \times \text{SWC} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Both normalized difference water index (NDWI) and root-zone soil moisture (also called soil water content, SWC) are commonly used in the literature as proxies of variation in vegetation moisture content (Zhang et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2022). NDWI is based on near-infrared (NIR) and short-wave infrared

(SWIR) wavelengths and is sensitive to changes in the liquid water content of vegetation canopies. Variations in whole plant water content are largely determined by foliage storage (Gao, 1996), and stem water content covaries with leaf water content, so that NDWI is a reasonable proxy of vegetation moisture content. Furthermore, since hydraulic transport should follow a gradient of water potential from soil to leaf (Bucci et al., 2004; Zhang et al., 2019), it is reasonable to assume that the possible interannual variability of vegetation moisture content is related to leaf water potential, soil water potential, and soil moisture.

Any terms in Eqs. 3-9 involving NDWI and SWC are the RWC-induced L-VOD changes, and Eqs. 4-6 include only the contribution of moisture content. In order to increase the sample size, multiple regressions were performed for 3-by-3 pixels spatial moving windows, leading to regression models of separating L-VOD variability. All the variables were normalized for each pixel before regression. Finally, the influence of moisture content was removed by subtracting the RWC-related terms according to the best model in each equation.

2.2 Results for correcting the effects of RWC in L-VOD

The model that included NDVI as well as NDWI and SWC (i.e., Eq. 9) had the highest coefficient of determination (R^2), on average, explaining ~36% of the variation in L-VOD (Fig. S24a), which is followed by the models using a combination of the two predictor variables (i.e., Eqs.6-8) with R^2 values between [0.23, 0.29]. In most cases, all the regression coefficients were significantly different from zero ($P < 0.05$), including the interaction term. The models that only include SWC exhibit very limited predictive power for the whole study areas (< 0.15 on average). We then calculated the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) of the different models (Fig. S24b), which can be used to evaluate how well the model fits the data. The best-fit model according to AIC is the one that explains the greatest amount of variation using the fewest possible independent variables (Stoica et al., 2004). As shown in Fig. S24b, the AIC differences among the seven models are very small, and the model that includes SWC and NDWI has the smallest AIC value. In fact, this is also the model that is considered to maximize the simulation of changes of vegetation moisture content signal.

The moisture content-induced L-VOD changes can then be removed by subtracting the RWC-related terms according to the best model in each equation (Fig. S15). It can be clearly seen that no matter which model is used to remove the contribution of RWC, it does not have a large impact on the inter-annual variability of L-VOD, especially the trend. Considering that the SWC×NDWI model explains L-VOD better than using any of these water proxies (Fig. S24a) and that it has the smallest AIC value compared to the other models (Fig. S24b), we ultimately used this model to remove the contribution of RWC from the L-VOD. The similar results for net changes in L-VOD-derived biomass carbon (BC) without and

with correction for moisture content (Fig. S16) confirm that the year-to-year changes in L-VOD mainly reflect changes in biomass, being only slightly affected by changes in water content on interannual scales. Additionally, after correcting for water information in the L-VOD, the overall trend change between corrected and uncorrected data was small with a median value of 5% and did not affect the direction of the trend (Fig. S17). This is in line with the results obtained in tropical intact forests using only one of the two vegetation moisture content proxies by [Yang et al. \(2022\)](#).

Text S3. Evaluation of the L-VOD-derived live biomass carbon product

To spatially and temporally evaluate our L-VOD-derived live BC data, we used biomass carbon data from the National Forest Inventory (NFI), a relatively accurate and independent resource.

1) Spatially

Spatially, we collected NFI carbon stock data from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) for each country in the study area in 2015. Fig. S25 shows a scatterplot of carbon numbers between L-VOD estimation and FAO reported numbers for the countries in the study area. It was found that, similar to the reference datasets, the total carbon estimated by L-VOD was close to the values reported by FAO. Overall, L-VOD had the smallest relative root mean square error (RRMSE = 20.70%) and the highest coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.99$, $P < 0.01$). With respect to the three reference biomass data, Saatchi's data was found to be more discrete and to underestimate in countries with relatively small total carbon than that reported by FAO, having the largest relative RMSE (RRMSE = 43.74%). However, this signature is less pronounced for L-VOD due to the fact that we used multiple reference datasets for calibration, resulting in L-VOD estimates that did not strongly rely on a particular reference data.

2) Temporally

Temporally, we collected NFI data on carbon stock changes during 2010-2021 submitted by Annex I (i.e., mainly developed) countries to the land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF) sector under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), as compiled by [Grassi et al. \(2022\)](#). These Annex I countries almost cover the study area (Fig. S19), and also have regular and continuous data. Note that 2021 was the latest available data at the time of this study. LULUCF is about the impact of human activities on forest carbon pools or fluxes ([IPCC 2019](#)), so each country submits data on the total live biomass of managed land forests. However, the delineation of managed forests in these countries are not open-access, although most countries, such as Europe, consider all forests to be managed. To address this issue and to achieve a fair comparison with the grid-based L-VOD BC, we used a proxy for the managed forest provided by [Grassi et al. \(2023\)](#) to remove the influence of the

unmanaged forest. As NFI data in most countries are revisited with a typical frequency of 5 years, this data source thus does not allow to capture interannual variability (Fig. S20). We here compared the net total biomass carbon change from LULUCF with that estimated by L-VOD for each country between 2010 and 2021 (Fig. S2). For these 27 countries (Fig. S19), the mean of the net change in total carbon estimated by L-VOD is 9.55 TgC yr^{-1} , marginally underestimating the LULUCF value of 12.35 TgCyr^{-1} . This underestimation can be partly explained by the fact that NFI data represent long-term biomass carbon change, since several years (typically >5 years) are required to revisit all plots within a national network. In addition, NFI primarily captures local biomass carbon changes in intact, mature, or old-growth forests, and does not account for carbon losses due to deforestation or degradation in the surrounding areas. Another reason could be that the NFI only samples within managed forest areas. We used intact forest boundaries as a proxy for managed forest, which may differ from what is actually applied by NFI in different countries (Grassi et al., 2023). Nevertheless, the biomass carbon changes in managed forests reported by L-VOD show a strong spatial correlation with NFI data from UNFCCC across countries ($R^2 = 0.58$, $P < 0.01$) (Fig. S2), adding confidence in our L-VOD BC product.

Text S4. A detailed comparison with three DGVMs

We additionally applied three DGVMs including JULES, OCN, and ORCHIDEE, each in two versions - one with prognostic fires and another with diagnostic fires - to evaluate the effects before and after including fire diagnostics and compare their consistency with L-VOD estimates (Methods). Spatially, across the northern ecosystem, the biomass carbon stocks modeled by ORCHIDEE ($r = 0.66$, $P < 0.01$), JULES ($r = 0.58$, $P < 0.01$) and OCN ($r = 0.56$, $P < 0.01$) generally agreed with those based on L-VOD. Notably, the L-VOD-derived BC estimates correlated well with the tree cover from Landsat (Hansen et al., 2013) ($r=0.81$, $P < 0.01$), while the three DGVMs, especially for JULES showed a noisier spatial relationship with this metric ($r=0.70$, $P < 0.01$) (Fig. S26). Temporally, the correlation between the three DGVMs and L-VOD BC showed a decreasing and then increasing latitudinal pattern over the 2010-2020 period, with lower values occurring between 50° and 60° N where fires are more prevalent (Fig. S27a). Interestingly, however, the fire-diagnosed versions of the DGVMs, especially JULES, demonstrated increased temporal correlations in this region compared to their prognostic counterparts (Fig. S27a,b). This suggests that DGVMs equipped with a diagnostic fire component could enhance the representation of fire regimes.

To further illustrate this point, we selected a boreal forest site where 47% of the area was affected by burning and 26% experienced forest loss in 2012 (Fig. S27d). It is evident that all three DGVMs with a diagnostic fire component showed a clear decline in 2012, aligning with the L-VOD BC trend, whereas their predictive fire versions indicated continued carbon accumulation. Nonetheless, post-fire recovery

in the L-VOD BC was less rapid than in the diagnostic DGVMs. As seen by the 30m Landsat imagery of the area, it is clear that wildfire impacts were still observable in 2016, but JULES has recovered to pre-fire levels (Fig. S27c). The slow recovery of BC after fires in the boreal forests, as observed by L-VOD, OCN and ORCHIDEE, is consistent with (Fan et al., 2023; Shvetsov et al., 2019). The L-VOD BC loss was further aggravated by the subsequent 2016-2017 drought (Fig. S27e), but this was not the case for DGVMs. This may be due to the insufficient response of DGVMs to environmental stresses especially considering the increasing VPD trends affecting rates of tree mortality, photosynthesis and fire frequency and intensity (Fig. 4f in the main text) (Wang et al., 2021).

Supplementary Figures

Fig. S1. Biomes in northern ecosystem as defined in this study according to <https://ecoregions.appspot.com/> (a), the one used by Yang et al., (2023) (b). In (c), biomass carbon changes in boreal biomes are plotted with the delineation from Yang et al. (2023). The net change in live biomass carbon in boreal biomes that we estimate over 2010-2019 is $+0.37^{+0.40}_{+0.33}$ PgC yr⁻¹, which is nearly identical to the results reported by Yang et al. (2023) ($+0.37 \pm 0.12$ PgC yr⁻¹), although they are based on global-scale calibrations. This further adds confidence to our estimated biomass carbon maps.

Fig. S2. Comparison of L-VOD-derived live biomass carbon with national forest inventories data.

(a) Scatter plot of national total carbon stocks in live vegetation biomass estimated by L-VOD and reported by FAO for 2015, as done in Xu et al. (2021). (b) Comparison of net biomass carbon changes between L-VOD estimates and UNFCCC reported values over managed forests in Annex-I countries during 2010-2021. RRMSE represents the relative root mean square error between estimated and observed total biomass carbon. The uncertainty in L-VOD estimates is represented by the intensity of the point color shading.

Fig. S3. Z-score variations from other datasets independent of L-VOD. Both Xu et al. (2021) (a) and VODCA C-VOD (b) data show a maximum in 2016 and a subsequent downward turn. The turning point shown by the gray line was determined by a piecewise linear regression. Trends were also determined using Mann–Kendall non-parametric trend test and Sen’s slope statistics. * $P < 0.1$; ** $P < 0.05$. Note that the available time spans for Xu et al. (2021) and VODCA C-VOD data are 2000-2019 and 2003-2018, respectively.

Fig. S4. Spatial patterns in L-VOD-derived live biomass carbon changes during 2016-2022. (a) Per-pixel gross losses, and (b) Per-pixel gross gains (Methods).

Fig. S5. Fractional gross losses and gains per year in the L-VOD derived biomass carbon data averaged per latitude during 2016-2022.

Fig. S6. The total live biomass losses in relation to forest area loss and burned area for each subregion of the northern ecosystems during 2016-2022. (a) Scatter plots of L-VOD estimated total biomass changes versus total forest loss fraction over the pixels with negative biomass changes between 2016 and 2022. (b) Scatter plots of L-VOD estimated total biomass changes versus total burned area over the pixels with negative biomass changes between 2016 and 2022. (c) Subregion boundaries in northern ecosystems as defined by the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report. The uncertainty in L-VOD-derived live biomass for a and b is represented by bars above and below the dots, indicating the minimum and maximum values of carbon change in biomass across the 12 calibration estimates (Methods).

Fig. S7. Spatial patterns of biomass carbon (BC) changes are shown for boreal biomes (upper panel) and northern temperate biomes (bottom panel), respectively. For each biome, three maps are presented: (a, d) BC changes from the L-VOD estimates, (b, e) BC changes predicted by the random forest (RF) model, and (c, f) the differences between the RF predictions and the reference data.

Fig. S8. SHAP interaction plots for temperate biomes showing the relationship between the change in incoming shortwave radiation (Δ Radiation) and Δ SM (**a**) as well as Δ VPD (**b**). Similar plots for boreal biomes show interactions between Δ Radiation and forest loss due to stand-replacing wildfires (**c**) and non-fire-induced forest loss (**d**).

Fig. S9. Hovmöller diagrams showing anomalies (z-score: (value – mean)/standard deviation) for northern ecosystems for each year and latitude during 2010-2022. a–e, Anomalies for 2010–2022 in LPDR X-VOD (a), ERA5 2-m air temperature (b), forest-loss area from Global Forest Watch (c), vegetation greenness (annually summed normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI)) (d), and ERA5 surface direct solar radiation (e), **f,** Spearman correlations between annual L-VOD-derived live biomass carbon stocks and annual soil moisture (green line) as well as SPEI (red line) averaged across latitudes from 2016 to 2022. The LPDR X-VOD results prior to 2012 are not presented due to the AMSR-E sensor failure in October 2011 and imperfect data fusion with the subsequently launched AMSR-2.

Fig. S10. Temporal variability in the area of forest loss as reported by Global Forest Watch (GFW), over the entire northern ecosystems (a), boreal biomes (b), temperate biomes (c) and the area burned by wildfires with tree cover >15% (d) during the period 2010-2022. The red stacked bar in subfigures a, b, and c indicates the area of forest loss due to wildfires. The forest loss annual increment is the Sen’s slope of the estimated trend line of change in annual forest loss. Note that the annual area of forest loss provided by GFW may not be continuous for several reasons. Here, we have used a moving average of the annual area of forest loss using their recommended 3-year window (<https://data.globalforestwatch.org>).

Fig. S11. Regional changes in drought indicators and L-VOD derived biomass carbon data. Anomalies for ERA5 soil moisture in 2022 relative to 2020-2021 (a), Anomalies for SPEI in 2022 relative to 2020-2021 (b), and Anomalies for ERA5 soil moisture in 2022 relative to 2010-2022 (c). d-e, Changes in drought indicators across years in the temperate biome for SPEI (d) and soil moisture (e). f-g, Annual variations in biomass carbon, expressed as the difference from 2010 values in Europe (f) Contiguous United States (g).

Fig. S12. Attribution of L-VOD-derived live biomass carbon losses across northern ecosystems and for temperate and boreal areas during 2016-2022.

Fig. S13. Changes in total industrial roundwood and fuelwood production reported by FAO relative to 2010 for the countries in the study area. Using estimated dry mass densities of 0.5 t/m³ and 0.45 t/m³ for industrial roundwood and fuelwood, respectively, the corresponding increase in harvested carbon between 2016 and 2022 is approximately 2.4 TgC for industrial roundwood and 4.6 TgC for fuelwood. Moreover, statistical analysis using the Mann–Kendall test and Sen’s slope estimator revealed no significant trend during this period, whereas L-VOD estimates showed a negative trend in live biomass carbon. On an annual average basis, the carbon extracted via timber harvest during this period was estimated at 0.27 PgC yr⁻¹ for industrial roundwood and 0.04 PgC yr⁻¹ for fuelwood, accounting for less than half of the L-VOD-derived biomass carbon losses attributed to non-fire stand-replacing disturbances ($-0.76_{-0.85}^{0.68}$ PgC yr⁻¹). This suggests that logging may not be the dominant driver of these losses, which could instead be attributed to other disturbances such as insect outbreaks or wind blowdown, consistent with findings in North American forests (Ma et al., 2012; Wang et al.2021). Timber harvest data were obtained from FAOSTAT (<https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FO>).

Fig. S14. Unburned and partly burned regions of northern ecosystems. Unburned regions were defined as SMOS grids (~25km) with annual fire area fraction less than or equal to 1% during 2005-2022. Annual active fire areas were estimated using MOD14A2. The remaining regions (annual fire area fraction larger than 1% at least one year from 2005 to 2022) were defined as partly burned regions.

Fig. S15. Regional average of annual L-VOD before (blue solid line) and after removing vegetation moisture content information, over (a) France and (b) Germany during 2010-2022.

Fig. S16. Spatial patterns of net changes in L-VOD derived biomass carbon, before (a) and after (b) removal of water content, their differences (c) and their scatter plot (d) based on the NDWI × SWC model during 2010-2022. Note that the "overall difference" in d represents the overall percentage of difference before and after correction for water information.

Fig. S17. Spatial patterns of trends in L-VOD derived biomass carbon, before (a) and after (b) removal of water content, their differences (c) and their scatter plot (d) based on the NDWI \times SWC model during 2010-2022. Note that the "overall difference" in d represents the overall percentage of difference before and after correction for water information.

Fig. S18. Density plots showing the spatial relationship between L-VOD and reference AGC datasets using (left) Saatchi AGC, (middle) GlobBiomass AGC, and (right) CCI AGC. The analysis is presented for different regions, including (a–c) the entire northern ecosystems, (d–f) the North American region, (g–i) the Europe part, and (j–l) the Russia part.

Fig. S19. Annex I countries with LULUCF data used.

Fig. S20. Temporal variations in annual biomass carbon in managed forests for L-VOD and LULUCF, over (a) Russia and (b) EU-27, expressed as differences from 2010 values. Note that at the time of this analysis, the NFI data had only been updated until 2021.

Fig. S21. Model performance when varying the ‘number of trees’ parameter from 25 to 1,500 in steps of 100, for (a) temperate biomes and (b) boreal biomes.

Fig. S22. Comparison of the RF model developed in this study with the Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model for northern temperate biomes (upper panel) and boreal biomes (bottom panel). (a, d), Relationship between observed net biomass change (Δ biomass) and RF predictions for the two ecosystems on the validation set. (b, e), Similar to a) and d), but predicted by the MLR model. (c, f), Variance inflation factors (VIF) for each variable in the MLR models for each ecosystem.

Fig. S23. Flow diagram of the filtering process.

Fig. S24. (a) Comparison of the coefficient of determination (R^2) of different models. (b) Comparison of the Akaike information criterion (AIC) indices of different models.

Fig. S25. Scatter plots comparing remotely sensed estimates and FAO-reported carbon values for countries within the study area in 2015, for (a) L-VOD based; (b) Saatchi; (c) GlobBiomass; (d) ESA CCI. Note that a total of N=43 countries were included, while countries with less than 50% L-VOD coverage due to filtering were excluded. RRMSE represents the relative root mean square error between estimated and observed total biomass carbon.

Fig. S26. Scatterplots comparing L-VOD-derived biomass carbon with Xu et al. (2021) biomass carbon in (a) and with tree cover data from (<https://glad.umd.edu/dataset/global-2010-tree-cover-30-m>) in (b). (c) shows the relationship between Xu et al. (2021) biomass carbon and tree cover. d-f, scatterplots between tree cover and biomass carbon simulated by the prognostic fire versions of three DGVMs including ORCHIDEE (d), OCN (e), and JULES (f). g-i, similar comparisons for the diagnostic fire versions of ORCHIDEE in (g), OCN in (h), and JULES in (i). Note that the correlations between L-VOD derived biomass carbon and ORCHIDEE, OCN, JULES simulated biomass carbon are 0.66, 0.56 and 0.58, respectively.

Fig. S27. Comparison of biomass carbon from L-VOD observations and simulations from three DGVMs. **a-b**, Temporal correlation between L-VOD derived biomass carbon and prognostic (**a**) and diagnostic (**b**) DGVMs during 2010-2020. **c**, 30m Landsat/Copernicus images acquired in 2011 and 2016 at a boreal forest site (latitude: 61° N -61.60° N, longitude: 88.20° E -88.60° E). **d**, Interannual variations of biomass carbon for L-VOD and different versions of DGVMs in the corresponding site, expressed as the difference from 2010 values. **e**, The corresponding soil moisture (SM) and VPD anomalies for this site.

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Parameters of the exponential function ($AGC=a \times L-VOD^b$) used to fit the spatial relationship between the benchmark AGC and L-VOD in Fig. S13.

Abbreviation	Benchmark AGC maps	a	b	r
Whole Northern Ecosystem	Saatchi	122.029	1.841	0.76**
	GlobBiomass	84.294	1.544	0.75**
	CCI	68.406	1.075	0.67**
North America part (20°W-180°W)	Saatchi	138.439	1.843	0.70**
	GlobBiomass	106.373	1.634	0.80**
	CCI	93.465	1.261	0.75**
Europe part (20°W-40°E)	Saatchi	122.959	1.763	0.81**
	GlobBiomass	105.913	1.394	0.80**
	CCI	89.411	1.170	0.74**
Russia part (40°E-180°E)	Saatchi	132.603	2.157	0.83**
	GlobBiomass	100.466	2.216	0.79**
	CCI	69.600	1.452	0.69**

Table S2. The predictor variables used in the Random Forest model for explaining the spatial variability of net changes in biomass carbon density.

Predictor	Abbreviation	Spatial resolution	Time period	Unit	Description	Sources
Soil moisture changes	ΔSoil moisture	0.25 degree	2010-2022	m ³ m ⁻³	Average soil moisture (SM) anomalies during 2016-2022 relative to 2010-2015	ERA5
2-m air temperature changes	ΔAir temperature	0.25 degree	2010-2022	K	Average 2-m air temperature (T2m) anomalies during 2016-2022 relative to 2010-2015	ERA5
Surface solar radiation changes	ΔRadiation	0.25 degree	2010-2022	J m ⁻²	Average surface direct solar radiation (SSR) anomalies during 2016-2022 relative to 2010-2015	ERA5
Vapor pressure deficit changes	ΔVPD	0.25 degree	2010-2022	Kpa	Average vapor pressure deficit (VPD) anomalies during 2016-2022 relative to 2010-2015	Derived based on ERA5 dataset using method in Yuan et al. (2020)
Photosynthetically active radiation	ΔPAR	5000 m	2010-2021	W m ⁻²	Average photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) anomalies during 2016-2021 relative to 2010-2015	Youngryel et al., 2018
Non-fire Forest loss changes ¹	ΔNon-fire forest loss	30 m	2010-2022	ha	Average non-fire forest loss area anomalies during 2016-2022 relative to 2010-2015	Hansen et al., 2013
Stand-replacing wildfires changes ²	ΔForest loss by fire	30 m	2010-2022	ha	Average stand-replacing wildfires area anomalies during 2016-2022 relative to 2010-2015	van Wees et al. et al., 2021
Soil nitrogen content	Soil nitrogen	250 m	Static	cg kg ⁻¹	Total soil nitrogen at 0-5 cm depth	SoilGrids
Soil clay content	Soil clay	250 m	Static	%o	Clay content mass fraction at 0-5 cm depth	SoilGrids

Soil organic carbon content	Soil organic carbon	250 m	Static	dg kg ⁻¹	Soil organic carbon content at 0-5 cm depth	SoilGrids
Water storage capacity	Water storage capacity	3 degree ×2 degree	Static	Mm m ⁻¹	Global water storage capacity	FAO
Tree cover	Tree cover	30 m	Static	%	Global tree cover data in 2010	https://glad.umd.edu/dataset/global-2010-tree-cover-30-m
Tree age	Tree age	1000 m	Static	year	Global 1km forest age datasets in 2010	Besnard et al., 2021
Species richness	Species richness	500 m	Static	-	Global forest alpha diversity map (local species richness)	Sabatini et al., 2022
Carbon turnover time	Carbon turnover time	0.5 degree	Static	year	Median of whole ecosystem turnover times across ensemble members	Fan et al., 2019
Human footprint changes	ΔHuman footprint	1 km	2016-2022	-	Average human footprint anomalies during 2016-2022 relative to 2010-2015	Mu et al., 2022

¹Non-fire forest loss is the removal of Hansen's forest loss from active fires detected in the corresponding year.

²Stand-replacing wildfires were updated from van Wees et al. et al., (2021), which is described in detail in the main text.

Table S3. Comparison of the net change in regional live biomass (PgC yr⁻¹) derived from this study with other recently published products.

Regions	L-VOD (2016-2022)	Xu et al. ¹¹ (2016-2019)	ESA CCI ⁵² (2016-2021)	Pan et al. ⁵³		
				(1990-1999)	(2000-2009)	(2010-2020)
Entire study area	-0.20 ^{-0.11} _{-0.26}	-0.63	-0.01	+0.50	+0.43	+0.28
Entire Temperate	-0.26 ^{-0.17} _{-0.33}	-0.33	-0.03	+0.27	+0.27	+0.24
Temperate (North America)	-0.15 ^{-0.10} _{-0.18}	-0.21	-0.04	+0.14	+0.13	+0.13
Temperate (Eurasia)	-0.11 ^{-0.07} _{-0.16}	-0.12	+0.01	+0.13	+0.14	+0.11
Entire Boreal	+0.04 ^{+0.05} _{+0.04}	-0.29	+0.01	+0.23	+0.16	+0.04
Boreal (North America)	+0.07 ^{+0.08} _{+0.07}	-0.09	+0.01	+0.00	-0.06	-0.03
Boreal (Eurasia)	-0.03 ^{-0.02} _{-0.04}	-0.19	+0.00	+0.23	+0.22	+0.07

For a fair comparison, the aboveground biomass provided by ESA CCI was converted to total biomass carbon using the root-to-shoot ratio applied in this study. Additionally, the inventory data compiled by Pan et al. (2024) excluded unmanaged and non-forest types and used a different biome classification from this study, particularly for temperate biomes. We included only their data for northern temperate biomes, excluding China.

Table S4. Root/Shoot ratio of below ground biomass to above-ground biomass (R) from IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories.

Domain	Ecological Zone	Continent	AGB	Root/Shoot ratio	Reference
Temperate	Oceanic	America	≤ 125	Conifer : 0.337 Broadleaf : 0.446	(Mokany et al., 2006 ; Gargaglione et al., 2010)
			> 125	Conifer : 0.338 Broadleaf : 0.190	(Mokany et al., 2006 ; Frangi et al., 2004)
		Europe	≤ 125	Conifer : 0.359 Broadleaf : 0.192	(Mokany et al., 2006 ; Skovsgaard et al., 2012)
			> 125	Conifer : 0.172 Broadleaf : 0.192	
	Continent	America	≤ 125	0.481	(Mokany et al., 2006)
			> 125	0.277	
		Europe	≤ 125	0.340	
			> 125	0.477	
	Oceanic Continental Mountain	Asia	≤ 125	Conifer : 0.243 Broadleaf : 0.225	(Luo et al., 2014)
			> 125	Conifer : 0.262 Broadleaf : 0.229	
Steppe	-	-	0.642*		
Boreal	Coniferous, tundra woodland, mountain Systems	-	≤ 75	0.390	(Mokany et al., 2006 ; Li et al., 2003)
			> 75	0.240	
Subtropical l	Subtropical Humid	America	≤ 125	0.175	(Mokany et al., 2006)
			> 125	0.284	

*Estimation from Mokany et al. (2006), not from IPCC

Table S5. Comparison of the reference biomass carbon (BC) and L-VOD derived BC data in 2012 using 12 sets of parameters for the same spatial extent over entire Northern Ecosystems, North America part, Russia part and the Europe part (the spatial extent corresponds to the one used for the calibration of the reference L-VOD / AGC relationships). The bootstrap cross-validated RMSE of the retrieved AGC stocks is shown in parentheses. The 95% bootstrap confidence interval is shown in square brackets. Spatial correlation (r) between the reference BC density and bootstrap BC estimates is shown on the right side of the table. The computation of the uncertainties includes only internal errors associated with each reference biomass map.

		Northern Ecosystem (NE) (Pg C)	North America (NA) part (Pg C)	Russia part (Pg C)	Europe part (Pg C)	r
Reference BC maps	Saatchi	89.0	37.4	43.0	8.6	
	CCI	89.9	40.0	37.4	12.5	
	GlobBiomass	74.6	32.1	31.8	10.6	
L-VOD derived BC	P _{NE} Saatchi	86.3(0.4) [85.7, 86.9]				0.74**
	P _{NA} Saatchi		36.2(0.3) [35.7, 36.6]			0.69**
	P _{Rus} Saatchi			42.1(0.2) [41.8, 42.4]		0.81**
	P _{Eur} Saatchi				8.6(0.1) [8.5, 8.7]	0.79**
	P _{NE} CCI	87.6(0.3) [87.1, 88.1]				0.63**
	P _{NA} CCI		39.1(0.2) [38.7, 39.4]			0.74**
	P _{Rus} CCI			35.0(0.3) [34.5, 35.4]		0.64**
	P _{Eur} CCI				12.5(0.1) [12.4, 12.7]	0.69**
	P _{NE} GlobBiomass	74.7(0.3) [74.2, 75.1]				0.72**
	P _{NA} GlobBiomass		32.7(0.2) [32.4, 33.0]			0.79**
	P _{Rus} GlobBiomass			31.2(0.2) [30.9, 31.4]		0.76**
	P _{Eur} GlobBiomass				10.8(0.1) [10.6, 11.0]	0.76**

** indicate significant correlations at $P < 0.01$.

Supplementary References

- Al-Yaari, A., Wigneron, J. P., Ciais, P., Reichstein, M., Ballantyne, A., Ogée, J., ... & Knapp, A. K. (2020). Asymmetric responses of ecosystem productivity to rainfall anomalies vary inversely with mean annual rainfall over the conterminous United States. *Global Change Biology*, 26(12), 6959-6973.
- Besnard, S., Koirala, S., Santoro, M., Weber, U., Nelson, J., Gütter, J., ... & Carvalhais, N. (2021). Mapping global forest age from forest inventories, biomass and climate data. *Earth System Science Data*, 13(10), 4881-4896.
- Brandt, M., Wigneron, J. P., Chave, J., Tagesson, T., Penuelas, J., Ciais, P., ... & Fensholt, R. (2018). Satellite passive microwaves reveal recent climate-induced carbon losses in African drylands. *Nature ecology & evolution*, 2(5), 827-835.

- Bucci, S.J., Scholz, F.G., Goldstein, G., Meinzer, F.C., Hinojosa, J.A., Hoffmann, W.A., Franco, A.C., 2004. Processes preventing nocturnal equilibration between leaf and soil water potential in tropical savanna woody species. *Tree Physiol.* 24, 1119–1127.
- Fan, L., Gao, Y., Brück, H., Bernhofer, Ch, 2009. Investigating the relationship between NDVI and LAI in semi-arid grassland in Inner Mongolia using in-situ measurements. *Theor. Appl. Climatol.* 95, 151–156. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-007-0369-2>.
- Fan, L., Wigneron, J. P., Ciais, P., Chave, J., Brandt, M., Sitch, S., ... & Fensholt, R. (2023). Siberian carbon sink reduced by forest disturbances. *Nature Geoscience*, 16(1), 56-62.
- Fan, L., Wigneron, J. P., Ciais, P., Chave, J., Brandt, M., Fensholt, R., ... & Peñuelas, J. (2019). Satellite-observed pantropical carbon dynamics. *Nature plants*, 5(9), 944-951.
- Fan, N., Koirala, S., Reichstein, M., Thurner, M., Avitabile, V., Santoro, M., ... & Carvalhais, N. (2020). Apparent ecosystem carbon turnover time: uncertainties and robust features. *Earth System Science Data*, 12(4), 2517-2536.
- Food and Agriculture Organization, Global forest resources assessment 2020: main report (Food & Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Rome, Italy, ed. 2, 2020), Global Forest Resources Assessment (FRA).
- Frangi, J. L., Barrera, M. D., Puigdefábregas, J., Yapura, P. F., Arambarri, A. M., Richter, L. (2004). Ecología de los bosques de Tierra del Fuego. Ecología y Manejo de los Bosques de Argentina. La Plata, Argentina. Editorial de la Universidad Nacional de La Plata.
- Gao, B. C. (1996). NDWI—A normalized difference water index for remote sensing of vegetation liquid water from space. *Remote sensing of environment*, 58(3), 257-266.
- Gargaglione, V., Peri, P. L., Rubio, G. (2010). Allometric relations for biomass partitioning of Nothofagus antarctica trees of different crown classes over a site quality gradient. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 259(6): 1118-1126.
- Grassi, G., Conchedda, G., Federici, S., Abad Viñas, R., Korosuo, A., Melo, J., ... & Tubiello, F. N. (2022). Carbon fluxes from land 2000–2020: bringing clarity to countries' reporting. *Earth System Science Data*, 14(10), 4643-4666.
- Grassi, G., Schwingshackl, C., Gasser, T., Houghton, R. A., Sitch, S., Canadell, J. G., ... & Pongratz, J. (2023). Harmonising the land-use flux estimates of global models and national inventories for 2000–2020. *Earth System Science Data*, 1093-1114.
- Hansen, M. C. et al. High-resolution global maps of 21st-century forest cover change. *Science* 342, 850–853 (2013).
- Jackson, T. J., & Schmugge, T. J. (1991). Vegetation effects on the microwave emission of soils. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 36(3), 203–212. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-4257\(91\)90057-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-4257(91)90057-D)

- Konings, A. G., & Gentine, P. (2017). Global variations in ecosystem-scale isohydricity. *Global change biology*, 23(2), 891-905.
- Konings, A. G., Rao, K., & Steele-Dunne, S. C. (2019). Macro to micro: microwave remote sensing of plant water content for physiology and ecology. *New Phytologist*, 223(3), 1166-1172.
- Li, Z., Kurz, W. A., Apps, M. J., Beukema, S. J. (2003). Belowground biomass dynamics in the Carbon Budget Model of the Canadian Forest Sector: recent improvements and implications for the estimation of NPP and NEP. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, 33(1): 126-136.
- Luo, Y., Zhang, X., Wang, X. P., Lu, F. (2014). Biomass and its allocation of Chinese forest ecosystems. *Ecology*, 95(7): 2026-2026.
- IPCC, Climate change and land: An IPCC special report on climate change, desertification, land degradation, sustainable land management, food security, and greenhouse gas fluxes in terrestrial ecosystems (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2019).
- Mokany, K., Raison, R. J., Prokushkin, A. S. (2006). Critical analysis of root: shoot ratios in terrestrial biomes. *Global Change Biology*, 12: 84-96.
- Momen, M., Wood, J. D., Novick, K. A., Pangle, R., Pockman, W. T., McDowell, N. G., & Konings, A. G. (2017). Interacting effects of leaf water potential and biomass on vegetation optical depth. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*, 122(11), 3031-3046.
- Mu, H., Li, X., Wen, Y., Huang, J., Du, P., Su, W., ... & Geng, M. (2022). A global record of annual terrestrial Human Footprint dataset from 2000 to 2018. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 176.
- Pan, Y., Birdsey, R. A., Phillips, O. L., Houghton, R. A., Fang, J., Kauppi, P. E., ... & Murdiyarso, D. (2024). The enduring world forest carbon sink. *Nature*, 631(8021), 563-569.
- Potithepa, S., Nasaharab, N.K., Muraokac, H., Nagaia, S., Suzukia, R.O., 2010. What IS the actual relationship between LAI and VI IN a deciduous broadleaf FOREST ? International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Science.
- Qin, Y., Xiao, X., Wigneron, J. P., Ciais, P., Brandt, M., Fan, L., ... & Moore III, B. (2021). Carbon loss from forest degradation exceeds that from deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(5), 442-448.
- Ryu Youngryel, Chongya Jiang, Hideki Kobayashi, Matteo Detto, MODIS-derived global land products of shortwave radiation and diffuse and total photosynthetically active radiation at 5km resolution from 2000. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, Volume 204, 2018. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2017.09.021
- Sabatini, F. M., Jiménez-Alfaro, B., Jandt, U., Chytrý, M., Field, R., Kessler, M., ... & Bruehlheide, H. (2022). Global patterns of vascular plant alpha diversity. *Nature Communications*, 13(1), 4683.

- Shvetsov, E. G., Kukavskaya, E. A., Buryak, L. V., & Barrett, K. (2019). Assessment of post-fire vegetation recovery in Southern Siberia using remote sensing observations. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(5), 055001.
- Skovsgaard, J. P., Nord-Larsen, T. (2012). Biomass, basic density and biomass expansion factor functions for European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) in Denmark. *European Journal of Forest Research*, 131(4): 1035-1053.
- Stoica, P. and Selen, Y., 2004. Model-order selection: a review of information criterion rules. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 21(4), pp.36-47.
- van Wees, D. et al. The role of fire in global forest loss dynamics. *Glob. Change Biol.* 27, 2377–2391 (2021).
- Wang, J. A., Baccini, A., Farina, M., Randerson, J. T., & Friedl, M. A. (2021). Disturbance suppresses the aboveground carbon sink in North American boreal forests. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(5), 435-441.
- Wigneron, J. P., Fan, L., Ciais, P., Bastos, A., Brandt, M., Chave, J., ... & Fensholt, R. (2020). Tropical forests did not recover from the strong 2015–2016 El Niño event. *Science advances*, 6(6), eaay4603.
- Wigneron, J.-P., Pardé, M., Waldteufel, P., Chaqzy, A., Kerr, Y., Schmidl, S., & Skou, N. (2004). Characterizing the dependence of vegetation model parameters on crop structure, incidence angle, and polarization at L-band. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 42(2), 416–425. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2003.817976>
- Xu, L., Saatchi, S. S., Yang, Y., Yu, Y., Pongratz, J., Bloom, A. A., ... & Schimel, D. (2021). Changes in global terrestrial live biomass over the 21st century. *Science Advances*, 7(27), eabe9829.
- Yang, H., Ciais, P., Frappart, F., Li, X., Brandt, M., Fensholt, R., ... & Wigneron, J. P. (2023). Global increase in biomass carbon stock dominated by growth of northern young forests over past decade. *Nature Geoscience*, 1-7.
- Yang, H., Ciais, P., Wigneron, J. P., Chave, J., Cartus, O., Chen, X., ... & Yao, Y. (2022). Climatic and biotic factors influencing regional declines and recovery of tropical forest biomass from the 2015/16 El Niño. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(26), e2101388119.
- Yuan, W., Zheng, Y., Piao, S., Ciais, P., Lombardozzi, D., Wang, Y., ... & Yang, S. (2019). Increased atmospheric vapor pressure deficit reduces global vegetation growth. *Science advances*, 5(8), eaax1396.
- Zhang, Y., Zhou, S., Gentine, P., & Xiao, X. (2019). Can vegetation optical depth reflect changes in leaf water potential during soil moisture dry-down events?. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 234, 111451.